

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SIX SIGMA AND STATISTICAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

This article investigates the integration of Six Sigma methodologies within the logistics sector, exploring its transformative impact on operational efficiency and overall performance. Six Sigma, renowned for its focus on minimizing process variability and enhancing quality, is examined in the context of logistics operations to ascertain its applicability and effectiveness. The study reviews key principles and tools of Six Sigma, highlighting its adaptability across various logistics subdomains.

The article emphasizes the importance of a cultural shift within organizations for successful Six Sigma implementation in logistics, requiring leadership commitment, employee training, and a sustained focus on continuous improvement. As logistics operations evolve in response to technological advancements and global complexities, Six Sigma emerges as a strategic framework capable of fostering a culture of continuous improvement and data-driven decision-making.

Methods: During the research process, historicity, scientific character, an objective and critical attitude to historical processes, and their comparative analysis were chosen as the main research methods.

Scientific innovation: Rigorous research into student achievement; the results were interpreted in the direction of addressing the core competencies of education.

Conclusions: In conclusion, the integration of Six Sigma principles into logistics operations has emerged as a transformative strategy to enhance efficiency, reduce variability, and improve overall performance within the supply chain. Through the systematic application of Six Sigma methodologies, logistics practitioners can identify and address process inefficiencies, streamline operations, and elevate the overall quality of services provided. This thesis has explored the key principles and tools of Six Sigma and their application in the logistics domain.

Keywords: six sigma, logistic, application, statistical application.

Introduction. The importance of the logistics sector is increasing as its growth potential is quite high. In Turkey, logistics is the second sector with the most potential after tourism. This reveals the strategic importance of the logistics sector for the development of the Turkish economy. Companies serving in the logistics sector within the scope of logistics activities; carry out material management, order-taking, storage, handling, and packaging operations. Logistics companies are expected to take into account the 7 basic rules that are the purpose of the logistics process while carrying out these activities. 7 rules- It is to deliver the right product, in the right quantity, at the right quality, at the right time, and at the right cost, to the right customer and at the right place. Ignoring any of these rules leads to customer dissatisfaction and therefore to a decrease in the company's competitive advantage and market share. It can be seen in the literature that various studies have been conducted on these rules.

Today, service-producing businesses have also increased their need for the 7P (product, price, promotion, people, physical facilities, and process) marketing mix to overcome the strong competition in the markets. One way to provide quality products and services that will increase customer satisfaction is to improve processes, which are among the 7P elements.

Therefore, to provide quality services, logistics companies must ensure perfection in all processes such as accepting orders, managing them, and solving problems. In most studies in the literature, customer satisfaction is determined by the survey method to improve the service quality of logistics companies. In this study, process improvement was taken as a basis to reduce return rates, which are indicators of customer dissatisfaction. Since processes in logistics companies have a complex structure, advanced methods and tools are needed for improvement. The Six Sigma method is one of these effective quality methods. With this method, it is possible to achieve zero error and provide error-free products and services that the customer wants. The method also enables the improvement in the process to be measured numerically with the sigma level. While the method was first developed and applied only to manufacturing processes, it has recently been widely applied to processes in different service areas such as healthcare, hotel management, and supply. In the study, the Six Sigma method was applied to a company that provides warehousing services in the logistics sector to reduce the returned products coming from building material stores that are its customers. In the problem addressed, the Six Sigma method was used because it is a customer-oriented method and it presents

the improvement of the current situation and the performance of the post-improvement situation in a numerical form by expressing it with the sigma level. The application aimed to reduce the return rate, which was initially 0.0007, to 0.0002 and thus reach the sigma level process of 3.54 sigma level. In addition, Six Sigma; By following the steps of define, measure, analyze, improve, and control, the reasons for return were determined and corrective action suggestions were developed.

Method: During the article's development, the author exerted considerable effort to systematically organize all sources and information through a detailed examination of specific historical analyses, aiming to construct a thorough understanding of the subject. Throughout the research process, the primary research methods emphasized were historicity, scientific rigor, and an objective and critical approach to historical processes. The author employed comparative analysis as a pivotal method to enhance the depth of the investigation.

Scientific innovation: Thoroughly researched student achievements; the results were interpreted in the direction of solving the main competencies of education.

Main part.

Six Sigma is a method that uses data and statistical tools to improve and maintain processes according to customer needs using systematic and scientific approaches. This method ensures the realization of the "zero defect" goal by understanding customer requirements, measuring and improving the quality of processes through the use of data and statistical analysis. Six sigma eliminates the variability that causes problems, develops permanent solutions, and ensures continuous improvement. (Abdullayev Edgar F., 2018: p. 26). In other words, it aims to eliminate errors in all product or service-related processes and operations.

The basis of Six Sigma is to constantly reduce the variability in products and services caused by small changes in production factors such as people, machines, materials and environmental conditions. For this purpose, change and its causes are identified and reduced or eliminated with corrective actions. Six sigma enables to reduction the defect rate in a process to approximately 3.4 per million, that is, to increase the defect rate to approximately 999997 per million. 3.4 defects per million makes the method valuable because it is very close to the zero defect level (Ballou, R., 2022: p.102).

In applying the Six Sigma method, the steps of define, measure, analyze, improve and control are followed, respectively. In the Define phase, the project is defined and customer demands and expectations are determined. In the measurement phase, the current state of the process is determined and data that can determine the root causes of the problems are collected. With the data obtained during the analysis phase, the difference between the current performance and the target is defined in order to determine the root causes of errors and improvement opportunities, and various analyzes are performed to determine the sources of variability. In the improvement phase, solutions aiming to eliminate the causes of the problem are developed and implemented. In the final control stage, the continuity of the solution applications, that is, their permanence, is ensured.

Failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA); It is an effective quality method that enables to identification, prevention and/or eliminates the occurrence of possible or known errors, problems and errors related to design, process, system, or service. With this method, which is a systematic approach that allows examining all aspects of an error, known and possible errors and their causes and effects are identified, the detected errors are prioritized according to the risk priority number (ROS) and corrective actions are developed. (George, M., 2023: p.90).

Table 1.

FMEA Probability Scale		
Violence	verbal expression	Degree
Very low	The customer is not aware of the error. There is no visible effect on the product.	1
Little	It is a mistake that will cause little dissatisfaction on the customer.	2-3
Middle	The customer is disturbed by this error. There is a noticeable decrease in performance.	4-5-6
High	There is a high degree of customer dissatisfaction. Disruptions occur in the process and service.	7-8
Very high	When an error occurs, it has a huge impact on the customer.	9-10

Source: By the author.

For example, there is only one company in the country's transportation sector that improved its processes by first applying Six Sigma and later by applying Lean Six Sigma. In the world, some activities are carried out on Six Sigma in the transportation sector. Although studies on the implementation of the Lean Six Sigma methodology have not yet made full progress, businesses continue their activities in reducing waste, which is the basic philosophy of Lean Thinking along with Six Sigma. In this part of the study, information about the profits obtained as a result of Six Sigma applications of some transportation companies that apply Six Sigma in the world will be briefly discussed.

Burlington Northern Santa Fe, one of the largest railroads in America, has developed a system called "World Class Maintenance" that includes methodologies including Six Sigma and Lean processes. The goal of the system is to eliminate idle time and improve labor and asset utilization, business process flow, material movement, and security of physical facilities. Mechanical and engineering groups at NSF have also had the opportunity to improve their efficiency through processes such as Six Sigma and Lean, which aim to reduce waste in maintenance procedures related to locomotives, freight wagons, rails, signals, and bridges. In this way, the opportunity to save more than 100 million dollars was seized.

Additionally, Six Sigma is used to examine the root causes and understand the errors of absolute sources. CSX has become one of GE (General Electric)'s leading transportation companies in America, thanks to the Six Sigma philosophy spread throughout the company. CSX generated \$17 million in annual revenue from projects related to service quality, industrial work orders, locomotive fuel, demurrage bills, and legal expenses. Six Sigma has become part of CSX's strategic plan and culture. While labor savings begin to be achieved thanks to the improvements in efficiency, the philosophy of reducing costs, which is important for the company, is also carried out by the people working in the Six Sigma team. (George, M., 2022: p.89).

By improving the process and using fact-based techniques to identify and eliminate waste, costs have been greatly reduced. In 2001, CSX saved more than \$20 million. The company also followed the path of developing this program. Thanks to Performance Improvement Teams and Six Sigma applications, CSX has implemented specific action plans to increase efficiency, offer new services, and reduce costs and has achieved its goals. 115 3.2.5.3. Norfolk Southern In October 2000, Norfolk Southern company announced its "21st Century". Launched an initiative called "Norfolk Southern for the 21st Century (NS21)". NS21 is an internal initiative launched to improve performance, focus on customer service, and reduce costs. Six Sigma was used together with NS21 and contributed to the growth of the railway. In 2003, Norfolk Southern refocused on what was called the 2nd version of NS21 and set new goals to improve the structure and density of rails, employee productivity, equipment costs, warehouse rationalization, and turnover growth. The company has also implemented the "Top Operation Plan" (TOP), which optimizes the way it operates the railway network by improving on-time movement, reducing the number of vehicle handlings, shortening routes, speeding up trains, increasing asset utilization, etc. In 2003, the first 3 cycles of the projects carried out within the framework of the NS21 program have been completed. A total of \$110 million in revenue has been achieved over the last 2 years, which includes savings on recurring costs of \$45 million. The earnings from 17 Six Sigma projects completed by 2003 amounted to approximately \$36 million and included concepts such as revenue increase and cost prevention. Additionally, better resource utilization and workforce efficiency have been achieved thanks to Six Sigma initiatives. By using the Six Sigma methodology, the maintenance process of locomotives has been improved, which has allowed for a reduction of train delays, reduced malfunctions of the machines' batteries, and reduced delays of in-service locomotives. (George, M., Dave-Kastle, B., 2015: p.12).

Union Pacific has been using the Six Sigma methodology for many years to increase customer satisfaction, reduce errors, and preserve energy. UP has not only achieved significant cost savings, but also made improvements in the quality of learning, training delivery, and project implementation. The company's

Total Quality Management system focuses on customers. The relationship between managing quality and improving customer service shows that customer satisfaction increases when costs decrease due to the reduction of rework and errors. Total Quality Management also includes Six Sigma tools to reduce errors. The Six Sigma project carried out in 2002, solved the wagon problem affecting automobile parts. In this way, customer satisfaction was achieved. In addition, it is aimed to protect the environment and natural resources by researching solutions to expand the use of diesel fuel or to cut locomotive emissions with the latest technologies.

Reducing variability, the basic philosophy of Six Sigma is an extremely important concept for logistics businesses. Logistics is related to managing stocks, and managing stocks is related to managing variability. When examining different types of inventory, it becomes clear that variability plays a significant role in how inventory is managed throughout the business process and supply chain. For example, safety or buffer stocks are held against uncertainties. Safety stocks; They are kept by businesses to avoid problems such as variability in supplier quality, transportation reliability, production process capacity, and customer demand patterns. In other words, if variability in the process from supplier to customer can be understood and controlled, reliance on safety stocks can be reduced. Lean Thinking has a very significant impact on logistics businesses. The most obvious mistake of the lean philosophy is that it finds application only in the production sector. The goal of Lean Thinking is to eliminate waste, reduce the number of goods waiting in stock to be completed, and respectively reduce the delivery times of the process and production, and finally increase the speed and flow of the supply chain. Another important cultural element of Lean Thinking that is important for logistics businesses is the concept of "total cost". Lean Thinking practitioners focus on total cost rather than focusing on transportation and storage, which are cost factors alone. While stock holding costs vary between 15-40% of total logistics costs in many businesses, making decisions based on total costs produces impressive results for logistics businesses. Both Lean Thinking and Six Sigma offer effective tools to the logistics industry. These disciplines and tools guide organizations in combating waste and inefficiencies. Although Lean Thinking and Six Sigma tools are very powerful, there is a need for a significant change of opinion on how Lean Thinking and Six Sigma operate in the logistics industry. First of all, decisions should be made based on the concept of "total logistics costs" and secondly, we should be courageous in eliminating waste.

However, organizational norms, traditional management approaches, and accounting financing methods struggle with the concept of "total cost" and continue to maintain natural tendencies toward the generation of waste. The Logistics Bridge Model is a model for the design and implementation of the logistics strategy based on Lean Thinking and Six Sigma principles. The Logistics Bridge Model is a compass that guides logistics professionals. It offers a

road map and comprehension ability for critical points such as the challenges of logistics in today's conditions and determining the route for the continuation of ongoing success. First of all, a bridge should be established with suppliers regarding the processes, and then the processes should be transferred to customers and a bridge should be established. While the aforementioned requirements are met, competitive forces and the pressures exerted by suppliers to reduce costs and increase market share should also be taken into account. The Logistics Bridge Model teaches that Lean Six Sigma in the logistics industry consists of 3 principles. These principles are: • Logistics Flow • Logistics Power • Logistics Discipline (Goldsby, T., Robert, R., 2015: p.90).

Conclusion

Six Sigma is a methodology that enables businesses to identify errors and variations in their current processes in line with customer expectations, determine sigma levels according to these error levels, and realize improvements using statistical tools to improve current performance. If the Six Sigma philosophy is adopted as a management approach in businesses, products, and services will be offered with close to zero errors, and at the same time, the satisfaction of customers who receive error-free products and services will be ensured. This enables businesses to carry out less costly, more profitable activities and gain an advantage over their competitors in today's competitive conditions. Lean Thinking, on the other hand, is an approach that identifies those that cause waste among the activities carried out, eliminates these wastes, and thus ensures process flow. Lean Thinking focuses on processes and increases speed and efficiency. It is seen that both approaches whose features are listed above provide positive contributions to businesses. For this reason, the Lean Six Sigma methodology emerged by bringing both approaches together. While Lean Six Sigma eliminates wastes that hinder the flow of processes, thus enabling fast and efficient processes to emerge, it also keeps the

variability in the process under control through the statistical techniques introduced by the Six Sigma methodology. In other words, unnecessary activities in the process are eliminated and statistical methods are used to eliminate the variability that prevents the process from functioning incorrectly. Lean Six Sigma methodology is used more widely in production enterprises because the flow of processes can be determined more easily, and today it has started to gain importance for logistics enterprises due to the increase in sectoral size and competitive conditions. Businesses that use Lean Six Sigma achieve significant cost savings and, as a result, achieve great returns. Issues such as reducing delivery times, achieving optimum stock levels, and increasing customer satisfaction, which are especially important for logistics businesses, are goals that can be achieved by adopting the Lean Six Sigma philosophy.

References

1. Abdullayev Edgar F. "Process improvement through Six Sigma", Baku, 2018, p. 26.
2. Ballou, Ronald, "Business Logistics Management", Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey, Prentice-Hall, 2022.
3. George, Michael, "Lean Six Sigma for Service", Mc-Graw-Hill, 2023.
4. George, Michael, "Lean Six Sigma: Combining Six Sigma Quality with Lean Speed", Mc-Graw-Hill, 2022.
5. George, Mike-Rowlands, Dave-Kastle, Bill, "Yalnız Altı Sigma Nedir?", S.P.A.C. Danışmanlık, 2015.
6. Goldsby, Thomas-Martichenko, Robert, "Lean Six Sigma Logistics", J.Ross Publishing, 2015.
7. Meriç, M., "Lojistik Hizmet Kalitesinin Tüketiciler Tarafından Algılanması ve Bir Uygulama", Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Kütahya, 2020, p.197.